

Response Header Hardening - Preventing Information Interception and XSS

Andrea Hauser

Offense Department, scip AG
anha@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

Marc Ruef (Editor)

Research Department, scip AG
maru@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

Abstract: The Referrer-Policy header indicates which information is permitted in the referrer header of a request. The Expect-CT header enables the implementation of Certificate Transparency. The X-Permitted-Cross-Domain-Policies header is used to allow PDF and Flash documents for cross-domain requests. The Access-Control-Allow-Origin as well as the Access-Control-Allow-Credentials headers should only be used for trusted sites using a whitelist approach. The Public-Key-Pins header should be avoided due to its complexity and dwindling browser support.

Keywords: Block, Browser, Flash, Google, Hacker, Hardening, HTML, HTTP, Identity, IETF

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2018 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20180308> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

This article continues where our previous discussion of response headers left off. We already stressed the importance of this topic *two* [1] and *three* [2] years ago. I would now like to focus on some lesser known and newer headers.

3. Referrer policy

The *Referrer-Policy* header is a fairly new header that has been a *W3C Candidate Recommendation* [3] since January 26, 2017. It makes it possible to control which referrer information is included in requests. When viewing a page, the referrer information indicates the origin of the request. Because this can lead to privacy and security issues when passing on the URL, the *Referrer-Policy* header was created to control how this information is sent from a referring page to the target page in the course of browsing. W3C explains the advantages of the *Referrer-Policy* header in the following situations, for example:

- **Privacy:** The URL might contain information that could be used to determine the identity of the user.
- **Security:** There might be URL-based session identifiers in the case of HTTPS. Or there might be so-called capability URLs, which only grant access to a resource to those people who know the URL.

The specification defines the following values for the *Referrer-Policy* header:

- `""` or *empty string*: This can be used to indicate that the *Referrer-Policy* header has deliberately not been set, in which case the browser is told to use another method for determining the referrer header.
- `no-referrer`: When this option is selected, no referrer header will be set for any request.
- `no-referrer-when-downgrade`: When navigating from HTTPS to HTTP, the referrer information will not be included. If, however, one navigates from HTTP to HTTPS, the referrer information is always included. This is the *default configuration* unless specified otherwise.
- `same-origin`: This configuration sends the referrer information only for same-origin requests. If there is a cross-origin request, no referrer header will be set.
- `origin`: The origin of the referring page is always included in the referrer information of the request. However, no information about the exact path is included.
- `strict-origin`: This rule is identical to `origin` except that the referrer information is not included when navigating from an HTTPS to an HTTP page.
- `origin-when-cross-origin`: This configuration tells the browser to send the entire URL in the referrer information as long as the request is "Same Origin". Any cross-origin requests will only pass on the origin without the exact path.
- `strict-origin-when-cross-origin`: Similar to `strict-origin`, `strict-origin-when-cross-origin` is a more restrictive version of another rule. The `origin-when-cross-origin` rules apply accordingly. However, the referrer information is also stripped if the request is sent from an HTTPS page to an HTTP page.
- `unsafe-url`: This setting tells the browser to send the full URL in the referrer header with each request.

We recommend using the most restrictive Referrer-Policy setting possible. Ideally, the header settings should be configured as follows:

```
Referrer-Policy: strict-origin-when-cross-origin;
```

4. Expect-CT

This header is currently only supported by Google Chrome and has *experimental IETF status* [4]. I will still briefly touch upon the concept of this header. In the *Chrome Status Platform* [5] it is explained as an HTTP header that allows websites to opt in to reporting or enforcement of *Certificate Transparency* (CT). If the Expect-CT Header is set for a web page, Chrome is told to check whether the website has a certificate in the public Certificate Transparent logs. This prevents fake certificates from being used on this website without being noticed.

5. X-Permitted-Cross-Domain-Policies

The X-Permitted-Cross-Domain-Policies header is used to permit cross-domain requests from Flash and PDF documents. In most cases, these permissions are defined in an XML document called `crossdomain.xml` found in the root directory of the web page. For situations in which the root directory cannot be specified, however, this header can be used to define a desired meta policy. The X-Permitted-Cross-Domain-Policies header should ideally be set as restrictively as possible. If integrating Flash and PDF documents via a different domain is to be prevented completely, it is important to ensure that there is no `crossdomain.xml` file in the web directory and that the header described is configured as follows:

```
X-Permitted-Cross-Domain-Policies: none;
```

6. Access-Control-Allow-Origin and Access-Control-Allow-Credentials

The `Access-Control-Allow-Origin` header makes it possible to control whether and which external pages are permitted access to the resources on a given web server. Permissions should be kept as restrictive as possible here. The configuration options are either to specify the trusted origin or `*` if the resource may be accessed by all. The `Access-Control-Allow-Credentials` header can also be set in addition to the `Access-Control-Allow-Origin` header if the content is protected using cookies or the Authorization header. Both headers should only be set specifically for trusted pages using a whitelist approach.

7. Public key pins (HPKP)

The advantages of *public key pinning* were already discussed in the article *Big Brother or How I Stopped Worrying and Love Encryption* [6], which made the following recommendation:

```
Public-Key-Pins: max-age=5184000; pin-sha256="base64-kodiarter-SPKI-Fingerprints"
[; includeSubdomains][; report-uri="URI"]
```

In my opinion, however, this article did not sufficiently address the risks associated with this header. If this header is set with incorrect PINs or the corresponding key is lost, users will be blocked from accessing the page. Because

correctly setting this header is not simple and the effects of an incorrect header can be disastrous, using it is no longer recommended. The suggestion *Intent To Deprecate And Remove: Public Key Pinning* [7] in the Chrome forum reflects this same opinion.

8. Other response headers

Below you will find the remaining response headers that we have already covered in detail in the past, as well as their recommended configuration. There is also a link to the article providing a more detailed description.

Strict-Transport-Security [8]

```
Strict-Transport-Security: max-age=63072000;
includeSubDomains; preload;
```

Content-Security-Policy [9]

If the content security policy has not been used before, we recommend starting with the following configuration:

```
Content-Security-Policy: default-src "none";
script-src "self"; connect-src "self"; img-
src "self"; style-src "self";
```

X-Xss-Protection [10]

```
X-XSS-Protection: 1; mode=block;
```

X-Content-Type-Options [11]

```
X-Content-Type-Options: nosniff;
```

X-Frame-Options [12]

```
X-Frame-Options: DENY;
```

Content-Type [13]

```
Content-Type: text/html; charset=UTF-8;
```

To conclude this section, it should be mentioned that it is equally important which headers are not set. For example, `X-AspNetMvc-Version`, `X-AspNet-Version`, `X-Powered-By` and `Server` can provide hackers with helpful information for attacking a given environment.

9. Current prevalence of headers

The headers discussed in this article are currently used to varying degrees: the prevalence of the `Access-Control-Allow-Origin` and `Access-Control-Allow-Credentials` header was not evaluated because they are not headers that should be found on every page. For this reason, evaluating the prevalence of these headers would not be particularly helpful.

Figure: Prevalence of the HTTP Security Header

The evaluation is based on data from *Shodan* [14]. In each case, a percentage is listed to indicate how many websites use the header. For example, only 0.2538% of all websites around the world contacted via TCP port 80 use the Referrer-Policy header.

10. External Links

- [1] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160121>
- [2] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20151217>
- [3] <https://www.w3.org/TR/referrer-policy/>
- [4] <https://tools.ietf.org/html/draft-ietf-httpbis-expect-ct-02>
- [5] <https://www.chromestatus.com/feature/5677171733430272>
- [6] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20151217>
- [7] <https://groups.google.com/a/chromium.org/forum/#!msg/blink-dev/he9tr7p3rZ8/eNMwKpMUBAAJ>
- [8] [https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20151217" title="HSTS](https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20151217 "HSTS")
- [9] [https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160818" title="CSP](https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160818 "CSP")
- [10] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160121>
- [11] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160121>
- [12] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160121>
- [13] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160121>
- [14] <https://www.shodan.io/>